

FROM “TÉDIO DE ALVORADA” TO “UIRAPURU” : ANNOTATIONS TO THE COMMENTED SCORE

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Abstract: From “Tédio de Alvorada” to “Uirapuru”: appointments to the commented score Premiered in 1935 in Buenos Aires' Teatro Colon under the baton of the composer, the ballet *Uirapuru* established itself as one of the most distinguished of Villa-Lobo's works, by its evocation of the tropical forest and its indigenous inhabitants and by the glare of its orchestration. And yet, *Uirapuru* is a reworking of a previous orchestral work, *Tédio de Alvorada* , composed in 1916/17, premiered in Rio in 1918 and performed successfully in Rio and São Paulo up to 1925, when it disappeared from programs. The authors will soon publish a study-score of the ballet where, by means of different colors, the original text from *Tédio de Alvorada* , its reworkings, new material etc will become immediately clear, together with analytical texts and the score of the first work . This article anticipates some of these observations.

Keywords: Uirapuru, Villa-Lobos, orchestral works.

Presentation

The ballet *Uirapuru* – premiered in 1935 at Teatro Colón in Buenos Aires, conducted by Villa-Lobos – became one of the composer’s most emblematic works, both for its evocation of indigenous and tropical forest themes and for the magic of its orchestration. . However, it is interesting to note that the musical text of *Uirapuru* , as noted by authors such as Luiz Fernando Vallim Lopes [2002], Paulo Renato Guérios [2003] , Paulo de Tarso Salles [2005 and 2009] , Maria Alice Volpe [2011] and Manoel Corrêa do Lago [2012 and 2016] , consists of the transformation of a previous work, dated 1916/17: the symphonic poem *Tédio de Alvorada* . This work, premiered in Rio de Janeiro in 1918, would be, in the following years, successfully

performed again in symphonic concerts at the Municipal Theaters of Rio and São Paulo , only to disappear from 1925 onwards.

With the purpose of highlighting the main insertions and additions introduced by Villa-Lobos when transforming *Tédio de Alvorada* in *Uirapuru*, in 1934 , the authors of this article produced a ballet study score, soon to be published, in which layers of different colors are used in the score to indicate the content of the original work, modifications and alterations of this content, and *Uirapuru* 's own thematic material . The autograph manuscript found in the Villa-Lobos Museum (MVL 1990.21.0172) was used as the base text of *Tédio de Alvorada* , which was digitized for this purpose and is published in the same volume. This same manuscript makes clear the operation of “bearbeitung” that the author himself made explicit when he signed the manuscript with the words: “Rio 1917 refurbished in 1934 - a process that was frequent throughout the work of Villa-Lobos. The study score is also accompanied by analytical texts that follow the genesis of the first work and technical and stylistic aspects of its subsequent transmutation.

Between the last public presentation of *Tédio de Alvorada* in 1925, - the year of its dedication to Ernest Ansermet -, and the world premiere of *Uirapurú* in 1935, we can identify a sequence of events that, plausibly, operated as “triggers” in the decision of the composer to “revisit” his symphonic poem of 1916/17, of which we present below a chronology in reverse order:

1934 - (October): having finished the score for *Uirapurú* , Villa-Lobos dedicates it to Serge Lifar .

1934 - (September): Lifar performs in Rio de Janeiro the world premiere of *Jurupari* , his choreography on the music of Choros no 10 by Villa-lobos, inspired by Amazonian mythology.

1934 - (August): arrival in Brazil of Lifar and his dance company, for a season of several weeks. Research by Lifar, at the National Museum, to support the choreography of *Jurupari* .

1933 - Villa-Lobos conducts in Rio de Janeiro, in the 1st Brazilian audition, the *Chant du Rossignol* (“Song of the Rouxinol”) by Stravinsky, whose scene of the “Song of the mechanical bird” presents textural solutions close to those adopted in 1934 , by Villa-Lobos when composing one of the two new sections for the ballet. It is not possible, however, to state at what moment Villa-Lobos began to envision the opportunity of making musical use of the uirapuru song, as recorded in Spruce's book, nor when he became interested in a narrative set in the Amazon forest, and in which the main character would be... a bird.

1930 - publication of the book by Gastão Cruls: “A Amazônia que eu vi”, which, citing excerpts from Richard Spruce’s book, reproduces his musical notation of the song of the uirapurú.

1930 - Conducting Bach’s *Brandenburg Concerto No. 1* in São Paulo, Villa-Lobos experimented, in a concert hall, with the use of the violin (replacing the "Violino Piccolo") as a solo instrument, and its timbre fusion with other orchestra instruments (an experience considered successful by Mário de Andrade).

1929-32 - Significant examples of “recomposition” of previous works (*bearbeitung*) follow one another in these years: in 1932, the children's ballet *Caixinha de Boas Festas* (transcriptions for orchestra of pieces from piano collections from the year 10: *Petizada*, *Wheel toys* and *Children's Carnival*); in 1931, the 5th String Quartet (*Cirandinhas*); in 1929, *Momoprecoce* for piano and orchestra (*Children's Carnival*), and above all *Amazonas*, based on the symphonic poem *Myremis*, contemporary with *Tédio de Alvorada* (and, like this one, set in ancient Greece and programmed in symphonic concerts between 1918 and 1925).

1929 - Joint premiere, in Paris, of *Amazons* and *Ameriques* by Edgard Varèse.

1925 - (July): Villa-Lobos, in Buenos Aires, donates the complete material (grid and instrumental parts) of *Tédio de Alvorada* to maestro Ernest Ansermet, dedicating the work to him.

1925 - (April): last public presentation, in the same concert, of *Tédio de Alvorada* and of *Myremis*.

Myremis/Amazonas case can be considered as the most important precedent of the *Uirapurú*, either by the operation of *bearbeitung* (including the inclusion of the violin-phone as an alternative to the zither d'arco), or by the conceptual reorientation of symphonic poem to ballet, and for the change (in the argument) in favor of an indigenous theme. Having witnessed so much an presentation previous in *myremis* how much, in 1930, that of *Amazonas* in São Paulo, Mário de Andrade left this comment on the process of transformation of one into another that seems equally applicable to the case of the metamorphosis of *Tédio de Alvorada* :

...the history of the Amazon is quite complex [...] It is an old [symphonic] poem that the composer remodeled from head to toe [...] If I'm not mistaken, this poem, which was about a text of Greek inspiration, has already been performed here, but was among the mediocre works of the composer [...] attributes to the same music the possibility of expressing Greece and the savage of Marajó, in the same way as Handel who, from arias of love, later made arias to Christ in the Messiah ...⁶

⁶in *Music, Sweet Music* [1930, 1963:154-155]

When comparing the works, attention is immediately drawn to the little relationship between the arguments that underlie them : while *Tédio de Alvorada* , of a contemplative nature (with the subtitle “About a landscape”) is set in classical Antiquity and describes the first moments from a dawn in the Peloponnese, the plot of *Uirapurú* is set in the Amazon rainforest and presents itself as a succession of adventures in which different characters alternate . And yet, despite this, the comparison between the musical texts of the two versions shows that the material from *Tédio de Alvorada* remains fully preserved (with variants and some rearrangement) in the body of the *Uirapurú* score , *making* it possible, therefore, to reconstitute its order sequential and demonstrate the musical correspondences between the 1916/17 and 1934 versions .

The musical text of *Tédio de Alvorada* was, until very recently, preserved in just one manuscript of the orchestral grid, with no excavated parts, belonging to the Villa-Lobos Museum (MVL P.38.1.2), of which a copy exists in the Music Department of the National Library , in Rio de Janeiro, the work of a professional copyist, as attested by the calligraphy and the beautiful finish, under whose title “about a landscape” was added in parentheses. It was only in January 2020 that a set of orchestral grids and a set of hollow parts was located by researcher Disuke Shibata in the archives of maestro Ernest Ansermet (1883-1969) at the Municipal Library of Geneva, Switzerland, also created by an experienced professional copyist. In addition to availability, which is decisive in itself, other factors, as will be seen below, led us to adopt the Villa-Lobos Museum manuscript as the basis for our understanding of the work and our work.

Several characteristics of the MVL P.38.1.2 manuscript suggest that it is more than unlikely that it served as the conductor-composer's score during the public performances of the work, which took place in Rio and São Paulo between 1918 and 1925. Among them, it is worth highlighting:

- the lack of concern with the exact definition of orchestration. The two pentagrams dedicated to the flutes would make us assume the presence of two; when we turn the page, however, we see that the second staff, in already abbreviated notation, is dedicated to flutes 2 and 3, which demonstrates that the suit is triple, not double. Similar small inconsistencies occur in various suits, such as oboes, trumpets, etc., many of which only the instrumental quantity is known throughout the work.
- the absence of typical conductor notes in front of the orchestra, such as input reminders, error corrections, etc.

- the presence of two pages , 8 and 9, almost completely blank, just filled in with some “scribbles”, which, in practice, makes it impossible to use them in front of the orchestra.

On the other hand, we find throughout the score a series of notes made in fine lines, by a fountain pen other than the copyist's (the aforementioned “scribbles”), many times adjusting notes and accidentals, other times modifying heights, altering the pitch. orchestration or even adding entire sentences to the original text. This characteristic indicates that this score served as a “working copy” in the process of transforming *Tédio de Alvorada* into *Uirapurú* . The discovery of the orchestral grid and play of parts of *Boredom* in Geneva confirmed this impression. Not only are practical problems related to its use in rehearsals and concerts absent from the latter, but, of course, the fine line notes are also absent - which we can now say are in Villa-Lobos' own handwriting .

For all these characteristics, and therefore also for the possibility of accompanying the process of transformation of *Boredom* in *Uirapurú*, the manuscript from the Villa-Lobos Museum was digitized and will be published in the same volume as the ballet study score.

With regard to new content, it is observed that the important additions embedded in *Tédio de Alvorada* all derive from the same 7-note “generator motif”, the “Canto do Uirapurú”, as noted by the English botanist Richard Spruce (1817-1893), on an excursion from Óbidos to the Trombetas River, from November 19, 1849 to January 6, 1850, and published in his book *Notes of a Botanist* , published in 1908 , which can be seen in figure 1.

Figure 1

Spruce, Richard: *Notes of a Botanist* (1908 p.102)

It is the incorporation of this new motif, interacting with the pre-existing material of the 1916/17 version, that will give rise to the main differences between the *Uirapurú* and the *Tédio de Alvorada* :

- in the “Introduction”, its appearance in the high register, in counterpoint to the main theme of the *Boredom of Dawn* (this one presented in the grave register);
- in the two entirely new sections (rehearsal numbers 5 to 8) corresponding, in the ballet, to the scenes “Canto do Uirapurú” and “Índias Dançam” .

Recomposing the true compositional feat represented by the superimposition of a given motif (the “Canto do Uirapurú”) to a previously composed musical text (the *Tédio* , itself) to function musically in such a sublime way, we focus on textually highlighting a few examples of the processes used by Villa-Lobos to transform, modernize, the work - the colored score being, of course, the true guide of this study.

- in the last two bars of page 2 , corrections are made by hand on the violas and threatened on the bassoons, making the SOL and FÁ of the *ostinato natural* , instead of sharps. Another hand-made addendum, on the eardrums, and in the same handwriting as the previous corrections, reinforces this new idea. One sees the composer's mind and hand at work here, clearly as on perhaps no other occasion. The original idea is to present the *ostinato* in 4 measures - as it occurs most naturally with accompaniment patterns in compositions of all styles, composers and eras - and so it is spelled by the copyist. In the process of transforming *Tédio* into Uirapurú , the composer decides to sophisticate the presentation of the *ostinato* by sketching a brief diversion (in the sense of a change of direction) on the score before returning to the original form over which the theme will be introduced. This is how the corresponding passage in *Uirapuru is presented*, now with the inflection reinforced by the second violins.

- in the *ostinato* of “Tempo in Marcia” (*Tédio* from page 2) / “Tempo di Marcia” (*Uirapur ú* from no. 3) , through the insertion of a simple rhythmic accent, even if magnified by a grandiose orchestration, the composer completely transforms the passage into an exotic *belle-époque dance* (would it be the “tropol of ghosts”? - Figure 2) for a powerful primitivist celebration (“Entram as Índias” - Figure 3; in black, the original text of *Tédio* ; in red, the modifications that transformed it into *Uirapur ú*).

Figure 2

The musical score for Figure 2 consists of nine staves. The top four staves are for percussion: 1. Tbn. (Tenor Trombone), 2. Tbn. (Tenor Trombone), Tmp. (Tom-tom), and Perc. (Percussion). The bottom five staves are for strings: VI (Violin I), VI (Violin II), Vla (Viola), Vc (Violoncello), and Cb (Contrabasso). The score is in 3/4 time and features a key signature of one sharp (F#). The first two staves (1. Tbn. and 2. Tbn.) are empty. The Tmp. and Perc. staves also appear to be empty. The VI (Violin I) staff has a 'Soli' marking above the first measure of the third bar, with a dynamic of *mf*. The VI (Violin II) staff has a dynamic of *p* in the second and third bars. The Vla (Viola) staff has a dynamic of *p* in the second and third bars. The Vc (Violoncello) and Cb (Contrabasso) staves have a dynamic of *p* in the second and third bars. The score is divided into three measures by vertical bar lines.

Villa-Lobos , *Tédio de Alvorada* , five bars after “Tempo in Marcia” .

Figure 3

The image displays a musical score for five bars of Villa-Lobos' *Uirapurú*. The score is arranged in a system with ten staves. From top to bottom, the staves are: Cor. 1-2 (Corns 1-2), Cor. 3-4 (Corns 3-4), Tbn. 1-2 (Tubas 1-2), Tbn. 3 e Tb. (Tuba 3 and Trombone), Tmp. (Timpani), Pn. (Piano), VI. I (Violin I), VI. II (Violin II), Vla. (Viola), Vc. (Violoncello), and Cb. (Contrabasso). The music is in 3/4 time and features various dynamic markings: *mf* (mezzo-forte), *ff* (fortissimo), *p* (piano), and *Div.* (diviso). The score shows complex rhythmic patterns and melodic lines across the instruments.

Villa-Lobos , *Uirapurú* , the same five bars after “Tempo in Marcia”.

- the last 3 notes for cellos and harp (left hand) on the penultimate page were originally written as MI, FÁ# and SOL, the latter having a confirmatory besquare sign, but have been corrected to MIb, FÁ# and Ab. There are a whole series of corrections that we can't decipher; the cello's second note, clearly a C# originally, has an annotation that could be a D or an F, and so on. Whatever the annotations may be , these are the marks of the passage's transformation into its correspondent in *Uirapur ú* (“Desolação das Índias”, ne25), and how Villa-Lobos makes the harmonic context more complex and richer .

However, perhaps the most revealing moments of *bearbaitung* in the work are those in which there are no structurally significant changes: the flute solo that begins the two pieces and the violin solo (in *Tédio*) / violinophone (in *Uirapurú*) that will be the “Aparição do Índio ugly” are practically identical in both works, except for repetitions and small melodic inflections.

Conclusion

The seventeen-year gap that separates the “mutation” of *Tédio de Alvorada* in *Uirapurú* associates two very distinct moments in Villa-Lobos’ creative activity:

- in 1917, his production, already exuberant and very personal, was in a phase of “melting” the influences of Puccini and Richard Strauss, of the Russian (mainly Rimski-Korsakov) and French (especially D’Indy and Debussy) schools, resulting in a language incorporating at times an accentuated chromaticism (tributary of Wagner, Cesar Franck and Strauss) with abundant use of altered chords and harmonies on the limit of diatonism (chords of 9th · 11th^{and} 13th); sometimes embarking on modal experiments (notably pentatonism and whole tones), parallelism of chords and non-functional chaining, tributaries of Puccini but above all of the French school (Debussy, Dukas). It is interesting to observe, in the production of this period, the prominence given by Villa-Lobos to a set of 3 symphonic poems, whose titles refer to an imaginary situated in classical Greece, and which - between 1918 and 1925 - are frequently programmed together, as if they formed a triptych : *Tédio de Alvorada* (future *Uirapurú*), *Myremis* (future *Amazonas*) and *Shipwreck of Kleonikos* . From this set of symphonic poems, two would be “recomposed” - *Myremis/ Amazonas* em 1929 and *Tédio de Alvorada / Uirapur ú* in 1934 - only the *Wreck of Kleonikos* remaining with the original language and aesthetics of the 1910s

- in 1934, when “reforming” his symphonic poem of 1916/17, Villa-Lobos does it through the prism of someone who had already incorporated works such as *Noneto* , *Amazonas* , *Rudepoema* , a *Prole do Bebê n ° 2* and , above all , the *Choros series* . As summarized by Paulo Guerios (2009, p. 293) :

[Villa-Lobos] completely transforms a work from the beginning of his career into one that has several characteristics of his musical maturity, lending it aesthetic boldness and thematic elements that he would only begin to use years later.

It is therefore from this double perspective - on the one hand that of the “composer of the Choro s” revisiting one of his youth works, and on the other hand that of an Indianism reformulated by “modernist landscaping ” - that the resignification of the symphonic poem *Tédio de Alvorada* in the ballet *Uirapurú* must be understood .

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